

EFFECT OF AGEING ON IMPACT FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF 2024Al-Al₂O_{3p} COMPOSITES MADE BY CASTING ROUTE

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ABSTRACT

Instrumented impact tests were carried out on 2024Al alloy and 2024Al-10wt.% Al₂O_{3p} composite in the as-extruded and aged conditions. Fracture toughness values (K_{Ic} and J_{Ic}) and the fracture energy values were computed from the impact test data. Results indicate that the fracture energy values give a better indication of the impact fracture behaviour of the material compared to the fracture toughness values. Both the unreinforced alloy and the composite showed higher fracture energy values in the underaged condition. The fracture energy values decreased with ageing and reached the minimum value in the overaged condition. SEM fractographs revealed that the mode of failure in the unreinforced alloy was a combination of shear and microvoid coalescence assisted by secondary microvoids formation along the ligaments in the overaged condition. The composites showed a transition in the failure mode from predominantly particle cracking in the underaged condition to a combination of particle cracking and particle-matrix debonding in the peakaged and overaged condition.

Keywords: aluminium-alumina composites, effect of ageing, fracture toughness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Studies on fracture characteristics of Al₂O₃ reinforced aluminium alloys have shown that particle additions generally lowers the fracture toughness [1-2]. Further, degree of reduction in toughness depends on number of variables such as particle size [3-5], volume fraction [5], matrix composition [3-6] and its temper [7] and also the method employed to measure the toughness. Our previous investigations [8] on fracture toughness of 2024Al-Al₂O_{3p} MMCs by instrumented impact indicate decrease both in the dynamic fracture energy and fracture toughness of 2024Al alloy due to the additions of 10 wt.% Al₂O₃ particles. These investigations have been done on composites in the as-extruded conditions without any heat treatment.

However, it is known that fracture toughness and fracture mode of aluminium matrix composite is markedly dependent on matrix temper affected by age-hardening [7]. The objective of this paper is to investigate (i) the effect of alumina particulate reinforcement on the ageing response of a extruded 2024Al matrix composites and (ii) to study the effect of different ageing conditions on the impact fracture behaviour of 2024Al- Al_2O_3p MMCs.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Materials

Alumina particle reinforced 2024Al alloy MMCs were fabricated with 10 wt.% of $18\mu m$ (average size) alumina particles (Al_2O_3p) by casting route. Cast billets were hot extruded into 13 mm x 13 mm square rods. The composition of matrix alloy, in wt.%, is 1.2 Mg, 4.88 Cu, 0.69 Fe, 0.23 Si with balance Al. Specimens were cut into 5 mm thick slices from these extruded rods. Thermal treatment was done on these specimens and ageing curves were established from microhardness measurements. Details of thermal treatments are as follows:

1. Solution heat treatment at 490°C for 2 hours followed by water quenching at room temperature
11. Age hardening at 175°C for intervals varying from zero to 15 hours.

For comparative purposes samples of unreinforced alloys were taken from extruded rods and subjected to identical heat treatment to establish ageing curves. Microhardness measurements were done on all specimens using a load of 100 gm. A minimum of six hardness readings were taken on each specimen.

2.2. Impact Testing

Standard Charpy specimens machined from extruded sections of both unreinforced and composites were tested using Dynatup instrumented impact unit according to ASTM-E23 method. Standard Charpy V-Notch specimens of 10mm x 10mm were used. The tests were conducted on the as-extruded, underaged (UA), peak-aged (PA) and overaged (OA) specimens. These different temper conditions were chosen from the hardness versus time plots.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Age Hardening Studies

The age hardening curves obtained for unreinforced alloy and 2024Al-10 wt.% Al_2O_3p composite are shown in Figure 1. The unreinforced alloy attains a peak hardness of 121.7 VHN in 6 hours while the composite shows almost same peak hardness in 4 hours. Here, composite exhibits an accelerated ageing compared to that of unreinforced alloy.

3.2. Impact Test Studies

3.2.1. Dynamic Yield Stress

The dynamic yield stress (Table 1) of both the unreinforced alloy and the composite attain the maximum value in the PA condition. Further ageing leads to decrease in their values. The dynamic yield stress values of the composite are found to be higher than that of the unreinforced alloy in both the as-extruded and the heat treated condition.

Table 1. Effect of ageing on impact fracture properties of 2024Al alloy and 2024Al-10 wt% alumina composites

Materials →	As-Extruded		Underaged (UA)		Peakaged (PA)		Overaged (OA)	
	Alloy	MMC	Alloy	MMC	Alloy	MMC	Alloy	MMC
Crack Initiation Energy (KJ/m ²)	64.4	29.4	100.8	40.5	95.0	98.9	53.3	25.9
Crack Propagation Energy (KJ/m ²)	110.0	79.9	110.3	89.8	101.4	73.9	93.6	44.8
Dynamic Yield Stress (MPa)	169.3	200.9	256.7	257.5	267.9	296.7	225.4	281.4
Elastic Fracture Toughness (K _{Id}) (MPa √m)	20.7	19.8	28.3	25.7	29.2	28.2	25.1	28.2
J-Integral (J _{Id}) (KJ/m ²)	17.3	13.0	27.6	15.3	24.7	13.0	18.0	11.3

3.2.2. Dynamic Elastic Fracture Toughness (K_{Id})

The present data revealed that decrease in K_{Id} values of unreinforced alloy due to presence of Al₂O₃ particles is marginal in both extruded and aged conditions. Both the unreinforced alloy and the composite exhibited the maximum K_{Id} in the PA condition (Table 1) and moreover it remained constant in OA condition in the case of MMC. This contradicts the results of Garret and Knott [9] on aluminium alloys who report maximum toughness in the underaged condition Table 1.

3.2.3. Dynamic J-Integral (J_{Id})

The unreinforced alloy is found to exhibit higher J_{Id} values compared to the composite in both the as-extruded and the heat treated conditions. Table 1 also reveals that the presence of Al₂O₃ particles in unreinforced alloy leads to large reduction in the J_{Id} values in contrast to the negligible decrease in K_{Id} values. Table 1 shows that the dynamic J-Integral values present a different trend

compared to the K_{I_d} values. Here the UA condition shows the maximum J_{I_d} value and it decreases with ageing for both the unreinforced alloy and the composite.

3.2.4. Fracture Energy Calculations

The elastic fracture toughness (K_{I_d}) and the dynamic J-Integral (J_{I_d}) values present contrasting results in the behaviour of unreinforced alloy and 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3 composite on ageing. Both the unreinforced alloy and the composite exhibit maximum K_{I_d} in the PA condition, but exhibit maximum J_{I_d} values in the UA condition. Girod et al. [10] have indicated that fracture energy values give a better indication of the fracture behaviour of metal matrix composites than elastic fracture toughness values. Hence to get a better picture of the material the fracture energy values are compared.

3.2.4.1. Crack Initiation Energy (E_m)

Both the unreinforced alloy and the composite exhibit maximum crack initiation energy values in the UA condition and it decreases with ageing time (Table 1). In the OA condition materials show least crack initiation energy. It is also clear that the crack initiation energy for the unreinforced alloy is more than twice of that of the composite.

3.2.4.2. Crack Propagation Energy (E_p)

Table 1 indicates the maximum crack propagation energy values in the UA condition for both the unreinforced alloy and the composite. The E_p values decrease with ageing time. It is also observed that in the case of the composite the crack propagation energies are twice that of the crack initiation energies while such a difference is not observed in the case of unreinforced alloy.

3.2.5. Fractography

Figure 2 shows the fracture surface of unreinforced alloy in the PA condition. The fractograph shows extensive microvoids present along the ligaments and also the regions of shear. Such extensive microvoids are not observed in the as-extruded and UA conditions. Figure 3 shows the fracture surface of unreinforced alloy in the OA condition. It shows a lot of large size microvoids. The fracture surface of 2024Al- Al_2O_3 MMC in the as-extruded condition is shown in Figure 4. This fractograph shows the alumina particles intact in the matrix without cracks or signs of debonding. The fracture surface in the PA condition of 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3 composite is shown in Figure 5. This fractograph shows particle cracking and particle-matrix debonding. But only particle cracking has been observed in the UA specimens. The fracture surface of the OA condition of 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3 composite is shown in Figure 6 and it also shows a cracked alumina particle with extensive microvoids along the ligaments around the fractured particle. Figure 7 shows a clear case of particle-matrix debonding in OA condition.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Ageing Behaviour

As observed in Figure 1, the composite shows accelerated ageing behaviour compared to the unreinforced alloy. This can be attributed to the increase in matrix dislocation density due to difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion of aluminium ($\approx 23 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and alumina ($\approx 8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$). It is also observed that the peak hardness achieved by matrix during ageing does not change due to the presence of alumina particles. This could possibly be due to the formation of Cu and Mg based spinels at the particle-matrix interface during processing [11]. This leads to depletion of Cu and Mg in the matrix thereby reducing the amount of age hardenable precipitates.

Fig. 1. Variation of microhardness (VHN) of 2024Al alloy and 2024Al-10wt.% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ composite with ageing time

Fig. 2 Fractograph of unreinforced alloy in peakaged (PA) condition

Fig. 3 Frctograph of unreinforced alloy in overaged (OA) condition

4.2. Impact Studies

The $K_{I,d}$ and $J_{I,d}$ values computed for the unreinforced alloy and 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3p composite present a very contradictory picture of the fracture behaviour of the materials. While the PA condition shows the maximum $K_{I,d}$ values, the $J_{I,d}$ values are found to be maximum in the UA condition for both the base alloy and the composite. Also, the elastic fracture toughness ($K_{I,d}$) of 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3p composite in the PA and OA conditions is found to be same. This raises the question whether the measured $K_{I,d}$ values for the 2024 Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3p composite is correct and appropriate indication of the mechanical behaviour. The fracture toughness is an appropriate measure of toughness of materials in which the onset of unstable crack growth dominates the fracture event. But, the process of crack growth can be affected by the additional processes like particle cracking, matrix-reinforcement debonding etc in the case of particle reinforced metal matrix composites. Hence in this composite, fracture energy values may be a better indication of mechanical behaviour.

Fig. 4 Fractograph of MMC in as-extruded condition

Fig. 5 Fractograph showing particle cracking and debonding in MMC under peakaged (PA) condition

Both the crack initiation and crack propagation energies show maximum values in the UA condition and they are found to decrease with ageing in both the unreinforced alloy and the composite. It is also found that the contribution of E_m and E_p to the total energy to failure is almost same in the case of unreinforced alloy. The decrease in the energy values to failure with ageing can be attributed to extensive micro-void formation along the ligaments (Figure 3) due to the precipitates which accelerate the linking-up of voids and the process of fracture. This explanation of decrease in the fracture energy values with ageing is also applicable to the composite. It is also observed that the contribution of E_p to the total energy absorbed prior to failure is almost twice of that of E_m . This indicates that the process of crack propagation is important in the failure of the composite whereas both the crack initia-

tion and the propagation have almost an equal contribution to the failure process of the unreinforced alloy. This can be attributed to the processes like particle cracking, and particle-matrix debonding (Figure 6 & 7) which increase the energy required to propagate the crack in the case of composite. It is also observed that the E_m values of the unreinforced alloy is almost twice of that of the composite.

Fig. 6 Fractograph showing particle cracking and microvoids in MMC under overaged (OA) condition

Fig. 7 Fractograph showing particle-matrix debonding in MMC under overaged (OA) condition

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. Accelerated ageing was observed in 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3p composite compared to unreinforced alloy. However, peak hardness values are same for both unreinforced alloy and the composite
2. It was observed that the fracture energy values give a better indication of the impact fracture behaviour of the composite compared to the elastic fracture toughness and J-Integral values
3. The fracture energy values of 2024Al alloy and 2024Al-10% Al_2O_3p composite decreases with ageing time. In both the cases, the UA condition shows the maximum fracture energy values and the OA condition shows the minimum fracture energy values
4. The mode of failure in unreinforced alloy was a combination of shear and microvoid coalescence. This was assisted by secondary microvoid formation along the ligaments in the case of PA and OA conditions. The 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3p composites shows the transition in the failure mode from predominantly particle cracking in the UA condition to a combination of particle cracking and particle-matrix debonding, in the PA and OA conditions.
5. The transition in the failure mode in 2024Al-10wt.% Al_2O_3p composites from the UA to PA and OA conditions could possibly be

attributed to the weakening of the interfacial bond between the matrix and reinforcement due to the presence of precipitates or depletion of solutes near the particle-matrix interface.

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